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**3rd International Conference on Pioneer and Academic Research
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Abstract Book

Fever-Associated Lethargy in Pediatric Respiratory Infections: Role of Neuro-Glio-Capillary Dysfunction

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Abstract – Acute respiratory infections (ARIs) in children are commonly accompanied by asthenovegetative manifestations—including lethargy, irritability, sleep disturbances, and cardiovascular dysregulation—despite the absence of direct central nervous system involvement. The underlying pathophysiological mechanisms remain insufficiently defined. This study aimed to examine the relationship between the intensity of systemic inflammatory response and neurological manifestations in pediatric ARIs, with particular emphasis on neuro-glio-capillary dysfunction as a key pathogenetic link. A prospective clinical study included 40 children aged 2–12 years stratified into three groups: Group A—uncomplicated viral respiratory infections with C-reactive protein (CRP) levels of 1–7 mg/L (n = 15); Group B—confirmed bacterial respiratory infections with CRP \geq 8 mg/L (n = 15); and Group C—healthy controls with CRP < 1 mg/L (n = 10). All participants underwent comprehensive neurological examination, vital-sign assessment, pulse oximetry, and laboratory testing. Comparative analysis of symptom frequency and severity between groups was performed using the Mann–Whitney U test. Group A demonstrated predominantly mild functional neurological symptoms, including lethargy (73%), mild tachycardia (40%), and increased tactile sensitivity (27%), with preserved consciousness and oxygen saturation > 95%. In contrast, Group B exhibited significantly more severe manifestations: impaired consciousness (33%), oxygen desaturation to 88–90% (27%), hypotonia and coordination disturbances (20% each), tachycardia (80%), and dehydration (33%). The mean neurological symptom burden per patient was significantly higher in Group B. A temperature threshold near 39.0 °C was associated with clinical signs of neuro-glio-capillary decompensation, particularly in bacterial infections. Neuro-glio-capillary dysfunction represents a central mechanism of fever-associated lethargy in pediatric ARIs. CRP > 8 mg/L, hyperthermia > 39.0 °C, and oxygen saturation < 90% may serve as early predictors of significant neurological involvement, underscoring the importance of integrated clinical monitoring for early risk detection and complication prevention.

Keywords – pediatric fever; febrile infections, lethargy; neuro-glio-capillary dysfunction; systemic inflammation; hypoxemia; neuroinflammation

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INTRODUCTION

We had the great honor of 3rd International Conference on Pioneer and Academic Research ICPAR 2026. It was truly a great pleasure for us to greet a lot of participants from many different countries to attend ICPAR 2026! We firmly believe that the conference will become an important international event in the field of cross-industry discussion about innovations in Academic Studies.

Three cooperating organizations supported the two-day conference. There were 107 papers accepted for presentation at ICPAR 2026, contributed from different countries. We had plenary speeches and several well-known scientists and experts, to give invited talks at different sessions.

The purpose of ICPAR 2026 was to provide a forum for the participants to report and review innovative ideas, with up-to-date progress and developments, and discuss novel approaches to the application in the field of their own research areas and discuss challenges of doing science.

We sincerely hope that the exchange of ideas on doing research, science and improving education will help the participants, and international cooperation sharing the common interest will be enhanced.

On behalf the Organization Committee of ICPAR 2026, we would like to heartily thank our cooperating organizations for all they have done for the conference. We would also like to thank the authors for their contribution to the proceedings; the participants and friends of ICPAR 2026, for their interest and efforts in helping us to make the conference possible; and the Editorial boards for their effective work and valuable advice, especially the ICPAR 2026 secretariat and the ICPAR 2026 staff, for their tireless efforts and outstanding services in preparing the conference and publishing the Proceedings.

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16-17 Şubat 2026 tarihlerinde MEET üzerinden çevrimiçi olarak gerçekleştirilen 3rd International Conference on Pioneer and Academic Research ICPAR 2026 konferansı akademik teşvik yönetmeliğinin 9. Maddesine istinaden “Tebliğlerin sunulduğu yurt içinde veya yurt dışındaki etkinliğin uluslararası olarak nitelendirilebilmesi için Türkiye dışında en az beş farklı ülkeden sözlü tebliğ sunan konuşmacının katılım sağlaması ve tebliğlerin yarıdan fazlasının Türkiye dışından katılımcılar tarafından sunulması esastır.” kriterlerini sağlamaktadır. Toplam 107 adet bildirinin yer aldığı kongre iki gün boyunca çevrimiçi olarak gerçekleştirilmiştir.

Türkiye dışından toplam 13 farklı ülkeden (Fas, Cezayir, Pakistan, Arnavutluk, Kuzey Makedonya, Libya, Hindistan, Tunus, Fransa, Birleşik Krallık, Slovenya, Kosova, Ukrayna) katılım sağlanmış olup, 107 adet bildirinin 60 (%56,07) tanesi yabancı katılımcı tarafından sunulmuştur.

Kongremize ilginiz için teşekkür ederiz.

Saygılarımızla,

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3RD ICPAR 2026 konferansı bilimsel komitesinin çoğunluğu yabancı bilim insanlarından oluşmaktadır. Aşağıdaki link ile bilimsel komite incelenebilir:

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Ayrıca konferansımızda hakem değerlendirmesi olup hakem değerlendirmesi olumlu sonuçlanmadan ücret talebinde bulunulmamaktadır.

2024 MART DÖNEMİ DOÇENTLİK BAŞVURU ŞARTLARI yönetmeliğinin 8. bölümde yer alan Bilimsel Toplantı tanımının b bendindeki “Diğer Uluslararası/Ulusal bilimsel toplantının düzenleme komitesinde, kurum/tüzel kişilik/karar organı tarafından resmi olarak görevlendirilmiş üniversite/enstitü/bilimsel kurum/branş derneği akademisyen temsilcisi bulunması zorunludur.” şeklindedir.

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Ayrıca görevlendirme yazıları ilgili konferansın özet ve tam metin kitapçıklarında yer almaktadır.

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